

Novel experimental set up to determine the optimal drug-coated balloon angioplasty parameters

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Abstract—In contradiction to the belief that drug-coated balloons deliver the drug uniformly to the stenosed vessel, literature suggests poor coating adhesion. Evidence indicates that, during the balloon inflation, the balloon-artery interaction has a key role in the efficiency of the treatment. Considering the above, the authors designed an *in vitro* set up able to account for procedural variables and assess their impact on the coating transfer efficacy.

Keywords—Drug-coated balloons, drug-coating stamping, mechanical contact, operational parameters

I. INTRODUCTION

Drug-coated balloons provide a promising minimally invasive solution, by advocating the leave-nothing-behind strategy and offering the potential to deliver the drug-coating homogeneously on the lesion. Nonetheless, studies suggest that the drug-coating is neither uniformly nor adequately delivered on the arterial mural surface, owing to poor mechanical contact [1], [2]. Therefore, it is consequential to comprehend the influence of the operational variables involved during the treatment on the coating transfer rates. On this basis, the authors developed an *in vitro* stamping set up to investigate the contribution of the contact time, pressure values, and balloon stretching rates on the delivered drug-coating percentage, with varying environmental parameters.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Materials

Artery: aortas was dissected from the porcine heart kindly provided by a local abattoir and was longitudinally cut to prepare 10x10 mm samples.

Artificial Plaque: 25% w/w gelatin gels [Type B gelatin powder from bovine skin, SIGMA] with and without 15-50% w/w hydroxyapatite [reagent grade synthetic powder, SIGMA ALDRICH] were prepared by using genipin [CHIBIO BIOTECH, China], a crosslinker, to obtain gels of varying stiffness up to 50kPa.

Balloon samples: rectangular films of PEBAX 7033 were prepared from granules, using a heat press machine. The PEBAX films were then spray coated with everolimus (EV)/Pluronic solutions of different drug/polymer ratios and then dried under vacuum to yield drug coated PEBAX films as drug coated balloon specimens.

B. Setup construction

The designed setup had an overall dimension of 100x167x220 mm (Fig.1). All the parts, except for the bolts and the guiding rods, were 3D printed in a Verve Kentstrapper 3D printer with a nozzle size of 0.4 mm and 0.02 mm vertical

resolution.

C. Set up philosophy

The setup consists of the top bed, where the pig aorta was flattened and glued, and the bottom bed, where the balloon samples were gripped. Each balloon patch was fixed at the grips, while the rotation of the lateral bolt caused a linearly increasing stretch on the sample. To control the contact pressure weights were introduced on the vertical axis of the top bed, considering the buoyancy force in the case of bath immersion. Experiments were performed by altering the parameters shown in Table 1, to study their influence on the coating transfer percentages. The drug coating transfer was studied by imaging the luminal surface of the aorta and the artificial plaque using an Olympus LEXT OLS4100 laser scanning digital microscope.

Fig. 1: Coating stamping setup

TABLE I
VARIABLES FOR THE COATING STAMPING EXPERIMENT

Parameter Type	Parameters
Procedural	Contact time
	Pressure
	Balloon stretching
Environmental	Temperature
	Saline/PBS
	Saline/PBS + Human Serum Albumin
Artificial Plaque	Medium with Fetal bovine Serum
	Stiffness

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